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Research Article

**EFFECTS OF ANTIHYPERTENSION MEDICATION AMONG
PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM HYPERTENSION AND WITH
OTHER CLINICAL CONDITIONS****Dr Syed Nasir Shah, Dr Sidra Zahoor**
PIMS Hospital Islamabad**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Hypertension is a very serious risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases. The evaluation of the effectiveness and safety of the anti-hypertension medication in different private hospitals is significant. This research work assessed the usage of Anti-hypertension medications among the patients present with hypertension alone or with some other clinical condition.

Methodology: This research work carried out on 400 hypertension patients who were recruited randomly from different private hospitals of Islamabad to assess the effectiveness and safety of the anti-hypertension medication. Diagnosis of hypertension alone or in combination with other clinical condition carried out in the patients. Patients from both genders were the participants of this research work. The collection of the data carried out from the medical history of the patients, conducting interviewing with doctors, nurses or by taking interviews of patients in the duration of this research work.

Results: The findings of this research work showed that most of the patients were males (87.50%). There was association of some factors with hypertension as profession, age and gender. 82% patients of hypertension were present with the history of hypertension in their family. We found no significant difference in diastolic blood pressure between patients of both genders (Average Diastolic Blood Pressure; 79.0 Vs 82.90 mmHg correspondingly, $P = 0.0760$), but we found a significant difference in average SBP between both genders (average SBP 149.0 Vs 138.0 mmHg correspondingly, $P = 0.0440$). The adverse reactions of the medications in this research work breathe shortness, headache, edema, dizziness, vomiting, and problems of gastro-intestinal tract and cramps of muscle.

Conclusion: There are many factors which are accountable for the contribution of the rise in blood pressure; most important risk factors are the life style and history of the complications in family. Combination treatment has association with very high rate of occurrence of adverse reactions of drugs; enough to permit either reducing the amount of medications or change in the prescribed medication. There is requirement of more efforts from the patients and professionals to reduce the danger of uncontrolled hypertension in our region.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension, Cardiovascular, Professionals, Medication, Adverse, Drugs, Complication.

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is most important factors for different cardiovascular and health diseases according to WHO (World Health Organization). This complication can cause various disorders of brain, kidneys, heart which results in stroke, inefficiency of renal function, MI (Myocardial Infarction) and heart failure [1]. In accordance with the findings of Stamler in 1993 and Ruilope and Segura in 2012 and European Society of hypertension with collaboration of European Society of Cardiology in 2013, monitoring of the blood pressure can decrease the various complications of heart particularly in the patients suffering from DM (Diabetes Mellitus) and inefficiency of renal function [2]. Published in MEDLAB Magazine in 2008, epidemiological research work on hypertension in Pakistan stated that survey conducted on more than 8000 participants and the overall rate of incidence of hypertension was 33.10% in public [3].

This incidence rate of the complication is very high. There is need to tackle this issue to reduce its occurrence in public particularly in elder patients. There is influence of other clinical condition on the treatment of hypertension as Diabetes Mellitus, renal inefficiency. Liau in his research work declared the olmesartan as highly potent and has a fast anti-hypertension impact as compared to Losartan for the treatment of hypertension from mild to moderate nature in patients of China [4]. Valarie in his research work stated that Amlodipine is much effectual and well-tolerated in the patients of elder as well as young age [5]. The purpose of this research work was to determine the effectiveness and safety of the anti-hypertension medication among the patients who got admission in the different private hospitals of Islamabad.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This research work was carried out on 400 patients from 5 different private hospitals of Islamabad. All the patients with the diagnosis of hypertension alone or in combination with other medical conditions, from both genders and from 20 to 80 years of age were the participants of this research work. This research work included the patients from all the

socioeconomic classes of the population. All these patients were present with a history of hypertension for last 10 to 15 years. All the patients present with pregnancy, AIDs, cancer or having less than 20 years or more than 80 years of age were not included in this research work. The duration of this study was from January 2018 to December 2018.

All the patients who were fulfilling the inclusion criteria and got admission in one of the five private hospitals were included in this research work. The collected information includes the file number of the patient, age, sex, height, weight, blood pressure at the time of admission, marital status, number of children, status of smoking, consumption of alcohol, history of the current illness, experience of exercise, load of working environment, history of medication, adverse reactions of the medication and occurrence time. The collection of the information carried out from the clinical history of the patients, or taking interviews of patients, doctors or nurses. Information about adverse reactions of drugs were collected from the patients and confirmation was provided by hospital staff. The data about the effectiveness of the medication was measured with the monitoring of blood pressure routinely. SPSS V. 20 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected data.

RESULTS:

There were 400 patients in this research work and 87.50% patients were from male gender. Average BMI was 28.0, average diastolic blood pressure was 82.0 mmHg and average SBP was 139.0 mmHg during hospital stay. 90% patients were married, 82.50% patients had offspring and 52.50% patients were non-smokers, 17.50% patients were smokers and 20.0% had left smoking. All the smokers were from male gender and most of the patients were the residents of Islamabad. There were 33.30% alcoholics. 92% alcoholics were males. About 82.50% patients were performing stressful jobs. The condition of the disease of patients and coexisting clinical issues are present in Table-1. 32.50% were doing physical exercise, and 85% among them were non-smokers.

Table 1: Distribution of Medical Conditions Vs Patients

Main diseases	Additional diseases													
	A	C	CH	M	O	CAD	N	K	DVT	H	IBS	A	L	T
Hypertension	0	10	0	0	0	20	60	10	10	0	0	0	0	110
Hypertension + Dyslipidaemia	20	0	0	10	0	10	80	0	10	0	10	10	0	150
No. of patients														
Hypertension + Dyslipidaemia + Diabetes Mellitus	0	0	0	0	10	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	50
Hypertension + Diabetes Mellitus	10	0	10	0	0	20	30	0	0	10	0	0	10	90

A: Asthma; C: Cancer; CH: Cholecystitis; M; Meat allergy; O: Odynophagea; CAD: Coronary Artery Disease; N: No additional diseases; K: kidney stone; DVT: Deep Vein Thrombosis; H: Hyperuricemia; IBS: Inflammatory Bowel Syndrome; A: Allergic rhinitis; L: Lung infections; T: Total

9 patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus and hypertension were not performing any kind of physical activities. 50.0% of plain hypertension patients and 47.0% patients of hypertension with dyslipidemia were participating in physical exercises. In this research work, 82.0% patients were present with the history of hypertension in their parents. Detailed age distribution with the incidence of hypertension is present in Table-2.

Table 2: Age Distribution

Age range	Frequency	Percentage
20-29	20	5
30-39	60	15
40-49	150	37.5
50-59	120	30
60-69	20	5
70-79	30	7.5
Total	400	100

Anti-platelets and lipid reducing, angiotensin converting enzyme-inhibitors, Angiotensin-2 antagonists, blockers of calcium channel, beta blockers were provided to the patient duration their stay in hospital. The name of these medication, number of doses and usage frequency is present in Table-3.

Table 3: List of Medications Given During the Study

Medication	Dose (mg)	Frequency	NOP
Valsartan	160	Once daily	120
Amlodipine	05 - 10	Once daily	80
Rosuvastatin	10	Once daily	70
Aspirin	100	Once daily	190
Flu vastatin	80	Once daily	60
Simvastatin	5-40	Once daily	120
Atorvastatin	20-40	Once daily	80
Clopidogrel	75	Once daily	70
Gliclazide	30-80	Once-twice daily	60
Losartan	50-100	Once daily	20
Lisinopril	10-20	Once daily	40
Esomeprazole	20	Once daily	40
Felodipine	05-10	Once daily	20
Fenofibrate	200	Once daily	10
Lercanidipine	10	Once daily	50
Hydrochlorothiazide	25	Once daily	150
Moxonidine	0.4	Once daily	20
Metformin	500-1000	Twice daily	50
Eosinophil	05-20	Once daily	30
Perindopril	5	Once daily	20

Atenolol	25-100	Once daily	80
Hydroxyzine	10	Once daily	10
Pravastatin	40	Once daily	40
Allopurinol	300	Once daily	10
Glimepiride	02-04	Once-twice daily	30
Amiloride	10	Once daily	10
Bisoprolol	5	Twice daily	10
Frusemide	40	Twice daily	20
Carvedilol	3-12.5	Once-twice daily	20

NOP: Number of Patients Taking the Medication

Table-4 shows the all the adverse reactions of drugs with each single medicine or combine treatment used for the patient. The percentage of the occurrence of adverse drug reactions in all the patients were not same; headache in 37.50%, fatigue in 37.50%, numbness in 10.0%, dizziness in 12.50%, shortness of breath in 5.0%, edema in 12.50%, muscle cramps in 15.0%, nausea in 17.50%, hunger loss in 7.50%, problems of gastrointestinal tract in 17.50%), chest pain in 12.50% and cough was present in 12.50% patients.

Table 4: Medication Therapy Vs Adverse Drug Reactions

D or DC	NOPUD	ADR1 (no.)	ADR2 (no.)	ADR3 (no.)	ADR4 (no.)	ADR5 (no.)
V, Ro, As, Si, Am, Hy	9	F	E			
V, Ro, As, Si, C, Hy	11	N	M	LOA	LOSD	
V, Ro, As, Si, Hy	8	G				
V, As, Fl, Ro	9	F	N	LOA	CP	
V, Fl, Hy	10	F	Nu	Di	Ba	
V, Fl, Hy, Le	10	He				
V, Am, Hy, At	10	Di	Ba	M		
V, Hy	10	Di	N			
As, Ro, C	10	He	F			
As, Ro, Am, Si	10	G	He			
As, Ro, At, Al, Hy	10	G	F	M		
As, Si, At, C	7	He	LOA	PU		
As, Si, C	9	N				
As, Am, Si, Fl	10	He	F			
As, Si, Fl, Le, Mo, Hy	10	He	Nu	E	G	Dm
As, At	10	He	N	Vd		
As, At, C	10	F				
As	40	He	G	F		
Am, Si, Hy	10	He	Di			
Am	30	He	F	E	M	
Si	10	He	F			
Si, C, Le	11	M				
Hy	12	F	Fe			

D or DC: Drug or drug combination; NOPUI: Number of Patients Using the Drug; ADR (no.): Adverse drug reaction and the number of patients reported to have the ADR. Drugs: V: Valsartan; C: Clopidogrel, Hy: Hydrochlorothiazide; Ro: Rosuvastatin, as; Aspirin; Si; Simvastatin; Am: Amlodipine; At: Atorvastatin; Le: Lercanidipine; Fl: Flu vastatin; R: Rosiglitazone; Mo: Moxonidine. ADRs: F: Fatigue; E: Edema; N: Numbness; M: Muscle cramps; LOA: Loss of appetite; LOSD: Loss of sexual desire; G: GIT problems; N: Nausea; CP: Chest pain; Nu: Numbness; Di: Dizziness; Ba: Bad breath; He: Headache; PU: Painful urination; Diabetes Mellitus: Dry mouth; Vd: Visual disturbance; Fe: Fever

DISCUSSION:

According to an estimation, more than 75% population of Islamabad is from 15 to 64 years of age. High amount of population is present from almost around the country. Most of the studied population in this research work was overweight [5,6]. High body mass index is the outcome of life style of the patients. There is also illustration that DBP and SBP has association with the body mass index. Adverse approaches of treatment and lack of knowledge are the reason in the rise of the rate of incidence of hypertension [7]. Less physical activity, low level of income, having three or more children and status of smoking are the main contributors in developing the hypertension in our population already examined by another research work [8]. 82% patients of current research work were present with the history of hypertension in their parents. Many other researches work also concluded the hereditary factors on developing of hypertension.

This research work showed that SBP and DBP difference was not significant [9]. This may be because these patients were wealthy enough to get treatment in hospitals as examined by Abdi Shakur in 2006. One other research work conducted on more than 12000 adults stated that beta blockers have raised the prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus by 28.0% and it was much higher than the patients who were present without medication [10]. One other research work concluded that combined treatment of beta blockers and thiazide diuretics enhanced the prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus by 32.0%. There is no adverse impact of Carvedilol and it also improves the MS (Metabolic Syndrome) as elaborated in comparative research work conducted by Bakris in 2004 [11]. So, it is important to avoid the use of beta blockers if the patients are suffering from Diabetes Mellitus and this fact was also examined by Padwal and Laupacis in their research work in 2004 [12]. One comparative research work conducted on combined treatment of aspirin and Clopidogrel and aspirin alone to the Diabetes Mellitus patients suffering from hypertension [13], discovered that combined treatment was more effective for such patients [14]. In the current research work, 67.50% patients were present with the development of adverse drug reactions [15]. There is need to take serious preventive measures to reduce the occurrence of Adverse drug reaction with the selection of pharmacotherapeutic alternatives as mentioned by Alomar in his research work conducted in 2008.

CONCLUSION:

Combination treatment has association with the adverse reactions of drugs with very high rate which is enough to permit the decrease in the amount of medication or change in the prescription of medication. Most important factor which influences

the compliance of patient and adherence to medicines is the existence of the adverse reaction of the drugs. There is requirement of multi-disciplinary professionals and patient's cooperation for the management of hypertension.

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